

Research Article

Indian cricket come into all attention than any other sport

B. Gowri Naidu¹, Ch. S. R. Naveen Kumar²

¹Assistant Professor, Department of Physical Education, Rajiv Gandhi University of Knowledge Technologies, Srikakulam, Andhra Pradesh, India, ²Assistant Director, Department of Physical Education, Rajiv Gandhi University of Knowledge Technologies, Nuzvid, Andhra Pradesh, India

INTRODUCTION

It is unpleasant but very true that one single game blotting many others games in India. Cricket fever overshadowed our national sport hockey. There is no question of any debate that cricket is killing other sports in our country. Indians eat, live, sleep, talk, and walk cricket. Theoretically, we all know that hockey is our national game but in practical vision, its cricket maniac all over.

India is a multisporting nation where a variety of games are played on a daily basis. Football, hockey, badminton, and tennis are mainly followed and played. Out of these cricket holds the majority share, both in terms of a man following and playing numbers. People in India absolutely love the gentleman's game and it is the most cherished sport in the country.

From kids playing it in the streets to the oldies having the fun of it at their home, cricket has grown to be a widely popular sport in India. People from all race, religion, caste, creed, color, and gender love to play cricket in India. The India National Cricket Team has brought a lot of laurels in the world in recent years and this is one of the key reasons behind the sports' popularity in the country. Today, we'll take a look as to why cricket has gained so much popularity in India and why people go bonkers behind the sport in the country. A numerous of questions in our minds why cricket is the most famous, popular and followed sport in India? Here was described various factors.

KEEP IT SIMPLE SILLY

To play the game, you just need a bat and a ball and a minimum of two players can easily play the game. It can be played even in the smallest of smallest dimensions, like a road, a street ally or even in a room. Reality check, in India, the sport is so

horribly popular among kids that they frequently play "gully cricket" even in most congested streets.

BETTER INFRASTRUCTURE

Compared to other sports, cricket has more number of coaching centers in the entire country. This factor is hugely responsible for drawing more and more young children, who aspire to be future cricketers. Similarly, almost in each and every state, there is at least one world-class stadium present whereas if we take a peek into football and hockey, there are only a few FIFA accredited stadiums and genuine astro turfs, respectively, present in India. This important factor also contributes to the increased participation and popularity of the sport.

VICTORIES AT MAJOR ICC TOURNAMENTS

India till now has won two ICC ODI World Cups, two Champions Trophies, one T20 World Cup. Moreover, with years India's performance in the cricketing arena has improved remarkably which undoubtedly makes India a reckoning force in today's cricketing fraternity. On the other hand, India used to excel in the game of hockey once but the country's performance in the sport has dwindled gradually. If we talk about football, India could never really make any mark in the world of football. The current FIFA ranking of India is 156 out of the 208 FIFA accredited nations which are more than enough to signify the poor state of Indian soccer. India's cricketing brand value is a huge reason for attracting a huge number of fans.

PHYSICAL QUOTIENT OR PHYSICAL ATTRIBUTES

A major reason why Indians are unable to compete with other countries in sports such as football, hockey, athletics, or tennis

Address for correspondence:

Ch. S. R. Naveen Kumar,

E-mail: naveensportsiit@gmail.com

is that we are not gifted with significant physical strength, good height, and substantial match fitness. The obvious reason behind this is the genetics which ultimately makes a big difference in these sports which are physically grueling. Our cricketers have more than enough strength and fitness in the body which enables them to play cricket at its highest level.

EMERGENCE OF WORLD-CLASS CRICKETERS OVER THE YEARS

India over the years has produced a bunch of world-class cricketing legends who at some point or the other have taken the cricketing world by storm. Batsmen, bowlers, all-rounders, captains consisting the likes of Kapil Dev, Sachin Tendulkar, Virender Sehwag Mahendra Singh Dhoni, Sourav Gangly, Yuvraj Singh, and Virat Kohli to name a few. Their pictures and posters are pasted over walls and are idolized by numerous boys and girls. Each of them is alone enough to inspire millions to join the game.

A STRONG GOVERNING BODY

Cricket in India is governed by BCCI, which is an efficient, rich, well-organized, and systematic council. The BCCI, over the years, has taken several constructive steps to protect and prosper the cricketing interests of India. It has been highly successful in establishing itself as a dominant body in the world. On the other hand, the governing bodies such as AIFF, HI, and IHF are highly disorganized and unmethodical when comes to functioning, and are often busy dealing with internal hassles. Their financial structures are also petty weak if compared to the BCCI. A strong backing helped it to emerge as the most popular sport in the country.

MONEY MATTERS

Money and cricket have almost become synonymous. Cricketers in India have always been the richer breed of sportsmen compared to their peers. Be it the salary, prize money, or government initiatives. The cricketers have always been ahead in the money race. With the advent of IPL, it was just another opportunity for them to get even richer. By virtue of being rich, the players can afford to have a better lifestyle, rather a lavish and posh one. This, unfortunately, has not been the case with the players, involved with other sports in India. Money is the most important requirement in any individual's life. Hence, whenever a career choice in sports is in question, it climbs automatically toward the sport.

SPONSORS AND ADVERTISEMENTS

Cricket is that sport in India which always has attracted a wide range of sponsors and advertisements as it's the most viewed

game. Even the players have made fortunes for themselves by endorsing several products and appearing in numerous commercials. Ever wondered why this happens in cricket and not in any other sport? A subtle thing it is, the few seconds break which is obtained repeatedly in between the starting and ending of overs or when a wicket falls, our television screens are flooded with heaps of advertisements. This period of discontinuity is not available in football or hockey or any other sport as they are continuative in nature. Thus, companies run after the sport and the people involved in the sport so that they can use those few seconds for publicity and ready to pay any amount of money for that!

EMERGENCE OF IPL FACTOR

In 2008, when Lalit Modi first introduced this T20 extravaganza, it instantly became a huge sensation. Since then, IPL has proved to be a game changer as well as a great money-spinner in the sporting history of the country. All the best players from the world assembled in India to play this elite competition. Moreover, it gave the platform to relatively unknown players to become a hero. Moreover, the amount of money and glamour involved in the competition would draw any budding players toward itself. The IPL has amplified the popularity of the sport to a gigantic level amongst the Indians as for now every budding player wants to be a part of the greatest show on earth. Although now, we have several parallel leagues like ISL, Hero Indian Hockey League, and Indian Badminton League and so on, they are nowhere near the fame or popularity of IPL.

CRICKET IS AN EASY AND FUN SPORT

Sure that, there are rules and regulations, just like any other sport. Those are necessary to make sure everyone is playing the same game and that there's no confusion as to how to play it. However, it does not take long to learn those rules. Once upon a time, kids were forced to play by exactly the same rules as adults. This quickly led to boredom and losing interest in the game.

Recommendations for Others Sports Most Famous, Popular, and Followed in India

- Sports and physical education make an integral part of school main curriculum with minimum number of physical education teachers/sports periods per week.
- In school, college, and university level, physical education must be treated as curricular subject not cocurricular subject/extracurricular subject.
- Provide basic infrastructures to every schools, colleges, and universities.
- Once sports becomes a part of school main curriculum, gifted, and talented students can pursue dual pathway (academics and sports) which may make it necessary

having basic infrastructure and coaching facilities at school, college university level as well.

- System for talent identification and development with long-term athlete development program.
- Increase and setting up of sports schools and regional academies.
- Increase incentives for sportspersons.
- Community coaching development.
- Strengthen the governing bodies and amateurs.
- Avoid political influence and transparent manner of selection of teams.
- Put qualified professionals in federation posts instead of honorary members.
- Graduating sports sector as an industry.
- Regulation of sports sector education program.
- Monetary assistance to the sports based firms.
- Provide land and invest in sports infrastructure through PPP model.
- Increase funds and tax holidays for sports-based firms.
- Giving a boost to R and D in the sports sector.
- Advertise and broadcast more sports.
- Strengthen the structured competition.
- Tie-ups with foreign bodies who have a vested interest in developing the sport.

REFERENCES

1. Available from: <https://www.bcci.tv>.
2. Available from: <https://www.icc-cricket.com>.
3. Available from: <https://www.sportswiki.com/cricket/why-cricket-most-famous-sport-india>.
4. Available from: <https://www.mbarendezvous.com/essay/cricket-vs-other-games-in-india>.
5. Available from: <https://www.signalsev.com/2020/08/5-reasons-cricket-is-indias-most-popular-sport>.
6. Available from: <https://www.youthkiawaaz.com/2019/04/under-representation-of-sportspersons-in-india-as-compared-cricket-players>.
7. Available from: https://www.en.wikipedia.org/wiki/Sport_in_India.
8. Available from: <https://mysportsmovement.com/sports/why-is-cricket-popular>.
9. Available from: <https://www.sportskeeda.com/cricket/5-reasons-why-cricket-is-so-popular-in-india-1>.
10. Available from: <https://www.mysportsmovement.com/sports/why-is-cricket-popular>.
11. Available from: <https://www.quora.com/Why-is-cricket-the-most-followed-sport-in-India>.
12. Available from: <https://www.sportskeeda.com/cricket/3-reasons-why-cricket-is-more-popular-than-any-other-sport-in-india>.
13. Available from: <https://www.thecricketpaper.com/guest-blogs/7066/top-5-reasons-why-cricket-is-so-popular-in-india>.
14. Available from: <https://www.m.dailyhunt.in/news/india/english/sportswiki+english-epapersptwiken/10+reasons+why+cricket+is+the+most+famous+sport+in+india-newsid-n199374854>.
15. Available from: <https://www.thecitizen.in/index.php/en/NewsDetail/index/12/17789/Why-Cricket-is-so-Popular-in-Indiaand-the-Famous-IndianCricketers#:~:text=For%20cricket%2C%20Indians%20have%20the,to%20play%20this%20sport%20competitively.&text=The%20popularity%20of%20cricket%20in,extra%20income%20from%20this%20sport>.
16. Available from: <https://www.sportzbusiness.com/how-to-improve-indian-sports-infrastructure>.
17. Available from: <https://www.sportskeeda.com/sports/10-ideas-for-improving-standard-of-sports-in-india>.
18. Available from: <https://www.area19delegate.org/10-things-india-need-improve-standards-sports>.
19. Available from: <https://www.entrepreneur.com/article/308261>.
20. Available from: <http://www.sports.ap.gov.in>.